

INFLUENCE OF VAZAVITAL ON INDICATORS OF COGNITIVE FUNCTIONS IN PATIENTS WITH DYSCIRCULATORY ENCEPHALOPATHY

Zhukovskiy O.

MD, PhD

Bukovinian State Medical University, Chernivtsi, Ukraine

ABSTRACT

The influence of the drug "Vazavital" on the indicators of cognitive functions in patients with dyscirculatory encephalopathy stage II was studied. It was established that after the treatment, the severity of subjective and objective neurological symptoms in patients decreased, the indicators of attention and working memory probably improved. The data of clinical observations and neuropsychological testing were confirmed by the results of an electrophysiological study - cognitive evoked potential P300.

Keywords: vascular encephalopathy, vazavital, cognitive functions.

Introduction. Changes in higher brain functions in patients with cerebrovascular insufficiency are considered to be one of the most reliable clinical criteria for the diagnosis of various, especially early, stages of dyscirculatory encephalopathy (DE). The pathological process in DE is not clinically manifested as an isolated complex of neurological and neuropsychological syndromes, some of them may remain subclinical until a certain time, being detected only when special tests and samples are used [8]. Vascular damage to the brain leads to a significant decrease in cognitive functions, and in the later stages, the ability to self-care of patients can also be impaired [3]. Chronic cerebrovascular insufficiency is accompanied by hypoxia and a change in the energy level of processes that store and reproduce information, which causes memory impairment. Memory impairment is one of the earliest and cardinal symptoms of DE. The neuropsychological defect in early DE is, as a rule, partial, and only separate pages of mental activity (cognitive, intellectual, affective sphere, etc.) are used. It is at this stage of the disease that the directed medicinal action can be particularly effective and cause compensation of the defect [3].

An objective criterion for assessing impairment of higher brain functions is a neurophysiological study, including the method of evoked potentials (EP). The feasibility of using the EP method in the comprehensive examination of patients with DE is justified by the fact that a decrease in cerebral blood flow and fully progressive ischemia of the brain can accompany changes in afferent conduction and indicators of EP. Cognitive, or endogenous, event-related potentials reflect electrical processes that are caused by the brain's own activity, mental cognitive functions: expectation, recognition, memory, information processing, decision-making, choice, etc. Cognitive potentials reflect the higher brain integrative processes of central processing of information and are objective indicators of the mechanisms of impairment of mental functions in a person [4].

For the purpose of complex pathogenetic correction of ischemic damage in DE, a large number of various drugs are used (antiaggregants, neuroprotective agents, nootropics, angioprotectors, neurotrophic factors, etc.) [9]. However, an additional task of treatment tactics is to limit polypharmacy, it is desirable to use drugs with a complex, versatile mechanism of action that can effectively affect various pathogenetic links. Among such drugs is Vazavital - a complex cytoprotector consisting of natural metabolites of substances and vitamins, containing nicotinic acid (niacin, vitamin B3,

vitamin PP), riboflavin (vitamin B2), pollen, pyridoxine (vitamin B6), rutin, thiamine (vitamin B1), ascorbic acid (vitamin C) and ginkgo biloba leaves, with antihypoxemic, antioxidant, neuro- and energy-protective effects. To date, the effectiveness of vazavital in patients with acute vascular pathology has been more studied, there is limited data on its effect on cognitive functions in patients with chronic insufficiency of cerebral circulation.

The purpose of the study. To study the effect of vazavital on the indicators of cognitive functions in patients with DE II stage.

Materials and methods. An examination of 28 patients with DE stage II, which developed against the background of cerebral atherosclerosis (CA) and the combination of CA with hypertension aged 52 to 72 years, was conducted. The diagnosis of DE was made according to the classification of vascular diseases of the brain [6]. Patients with gross motor or sensory disorders, with severe somatic diseases, with other clinically significant neurological or mental diseases were not included in the study. The patients were not prescribed other drugs that affect cognitive functions (central cholinesterase inhibitors, nootropics).

All patients were randomly divided into two groups. 12 patients of the I group received standardized medical treatment without the use of nootropic drugs, and 16 patients of the II group received Vazavital in a dose of 1 capsule 3 times a day for 2 months. All patients were examined for their neurological status using a score. The neuropsychological study included: the study of attention using the "Searching for numbers according to Schulte's tables" technique with an assessment of the task completion time; research of mental capacity according to the "Serial Score 100-7" method with an assessment of the test execution time and the number of errors; memory research using the "Memorization of ten words" method [5].

The state of cognitive evoked potentials was studied with the help of the multifunctional computer complex "Neuro-MVP". The electrodes were located according to the international "10-20" scheme. For the study of cognitive EPs, the subjects were instructed to count the number of "significant" stimuli (sound signals with a tone frequency of 2000 Hz and a probability of delivery of up to 30%), not paying attention to "insignificant" ones with a tone frequency of 1000 Hz and a probability of delivery of 70% or more. When obtaining the results, the shape of the curve, the presence of

all components, indicators of latent periods and the amplitude of potential components were evaluated.

The examination was carried out before treatment (on the 1st day of observation) and after the therapy (on the 60th day). The research was carried out in compliance with the provisions of the Council of Europe Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine and the recommendations of the Committee on Bioethics under the Presidium of the Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine. Statistical processing of the research results was carried out by the method of variational statistics using the Student's t test. The results were considered reliable at $p < 0.05$.

Research results and their discussion.

Most often, patients with DE stage II complained of headache (92.8% of patients) and memory impairment (85.7% of patients). The headache was almost constant, intense and less dependent on emotional or physical overload, on weather conditions. A significant part of the patients (82.1%) complained of dizziness, often unsystematic, unsteadiness when walking, tinnitus, visual disturbances in the form of dark circles, flickering "flies" in front of the eyes, heaviness in the head, more in the morning. During an objective neurological examination, signs of damage to all levels of the brain were observed in DE patients: cortical, subcortical, hypothalamic, stem-cerebellar. After the treatment, a clear positive dynamic of subjective and objective neurological symptoms was revealed. As a result of treatment with vazavital, headache decreased in 50% of observations, dizziness - in 60%, 90% of patients noted an increase in physical and mental capacity, 45% of patients noted normalization of sleep, and 10% - a decrease in anxiety. In the comparison group, a decrease in headache and dizziness was noted in 50% of observations. After treatment, ataxic disorders decreased in 30% of patients in the main group and in 20% of patients receiving basic treatment.

In patients with DE stage II on the background of CA after treatment, attention and the ability to perform calculations according to the Kripelin test improved: by 15.7% in patients who received basic treatment and by 27.0% in the group of patients who received Vazavital. In the II group of patients, after treatment, the speed of finding numbers in the Schulte table increased by 26.8% and in the Gorbov table by 14.8%, which indicates an improvement in the stability and speed of switching attention, as well as an improvement in the mental capacity of the patients. In the group of patients who received basic treatment, only a tendency to improve these indicators was observed. Patients with CA who received basic treatment reproduced 4.3% more words after the first reading than before treatment, and after the fifth - 9.8% more words (7.63 ± 0.46). Long-term memory also increased by 12.9%. In the group of patients who received Vazavital, the curve took on an increasing character, the productivity of memorization increased. After the first reading, patients reproduced 22.4% more words than before treatment. The number of reproduced words increased significantly after the fourth (by 16.9%) and fifth readings (by 28.1%). Long-term memory improved by 28.5%. All indicators in this group have changed significantly.

In the group of patients with DE stage II, which developed against the background of CA and hypertension, who received Vazavital, a significant improvement in attention indicators was observed according to the Kripelin test by 29.0%, according to the Schulte tables - by 26.8%, according to the Gorbov table - by 22.2%. According to the "Remembering 10 words" test, a tendency to improve short-term and long-term memory was observed in both groups, more pronounced in the group of patients receiving Vazavital. Patients with DE, which developed on the background of CA with hypertension, who received basic treatment, named 15.6% more words after the first reading than before treatment, and patients who were prescribed complex therapy with Vazavital - 19.8% more words. Accordingly, after the fifth reading - by 9.0% (7.25 ± 0.37 words) and by 17.1% (7.79 ± 0.48 words) more. Long-term memory increased after basic treatment by 5.2%, and after taking Vazavital by 12.1%.

When determining the cognitive EP in the examined patients before treatment, the indicator of the late P300 component was 420 ms on average, which indicates a violation of cognitive functions in these patients.

When analyzing the results of cognitive EPs after treatment in the first group, a decrease in the latent period of the P3 component was found by 8.6% ($p > 0.05$), and in the second - by 10.8% ($p < 0.05$), which indicates more pronounced improvement of cognitive functions in patients of the second group.

Conclusions. 1. In patients with DE stage II, complex treatment with the use of Vazavital causes a probable improvement in indicators of attention, short-term and long-term memory.

2. The positive effect of Vazavital on cognitive functions is confirmed by the reduction of the latent period of the P300 component in the study of cognitive evoked potentials.

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